

Soft Skills for Software Engineer

1. Communication (96%)	
Nomenclature	References
Communication	(HAZZAN, 2021; GROENEVELD et al., 2021; TAYLOR, 2019; BYRNE et al., 2020; FREITAS et al., 2018; VAN LAAR et al., 2017; SEDELMAIER and LANDES, 2014; AHMED et al., 2012)
Communication (oral/written)	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; GAROUSI et al., 2019; CARTER, 2011)
Presentation	(MATTURRO et al., 2019; SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; ZHENG et al., 2015)
Communication skills	(STRAY et al., 2021; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
External and internal communication	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020)
Communicate effectively	(VALERO et al., 2020; CUKIERMAN and PALMIERI, 2014)
Report writing	(GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
2. Teamwork (74%)	
Nomenclature	References
Teamwork	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; GAROUSI et al., 2019; SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; MATTURRO et al., 2015; ZHENG et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; AHMED et al., 2012; GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011; CARTER, 2011)
Collaboration with others	(VAN LAAR et al., 2017; SEDELMAIER and LANDES, 2014)
Teamwork and collaboration	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KHAKUREL, PORRAS, 2020)
Work in teams	(VALERO et al., 2020)
Relações interpessoais e trabalho em equipe	(TAYLOR, 2019)
Team management	(FREITAS et al., 2018)
To perform effectively in teams	(CUKIERMAN and PALMIERI, 2014)
3. Organization (70%)	
Nomenclature	References
Organization skills	(HAZZAN, 2021; KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; AHMED et al., 2012; CARTER, 2011)
Planning	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; MATTURRO et al., 2019; ZHENG et al., 2015; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
Time Management	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; FREITAS et al., 2018; ZHENG et al., 2015)
Time and work management	(VALERO et al., 2020)
4. Leadership (65%)	
Nomenclature	References
Leadership	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; BYRNE et al., 2020; KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; GAROUSI et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2019; FREITAS et al., 2018; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; CARTER, 2011)
Ability to coordinate teams	(HAZZAN, 2021)
Team management	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; MATTURRO et al., 2019)
Leadership and emotional intelligence	(TAYLOR, 2019)

Leadership and supervision	(GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
5. Learning (65%)	
Nomenclature	References
Willingness/eagerness to learn	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
To learn continuously	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; CUKIERMAN and PALMIERI, 2014)
Fast learning	(HAZZAN, 2021; MATTURRO et al., 2019; AHMED et al., 2012)
Curiosity	(STRAY et al., 2021; GROENEVELD et al., 2021)
Learn	(VAN LAAR et al., 2017)
Learning	(ZHENG et al., 2015)
6. Creativity (61%)	
Nomenclature	References
Creativity	(STRAY et al., 2021; GROENEVELD et al., 2021; CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; VALERO et al., 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; VAN LAAR et al., 2017; CARTER, 2011; CARROLL et al., 2007)
Innovation	(HAZZAN, 2021; BYRNE et al., 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; VAN LAAR et al., 2017)
Creativity and innovation	(SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018)
7. Critical thinking (48%)	
Nomenclature	References
Critical thinking	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; GAROUSI et al., 2019; HAZZAN, 2021; GROENEVELD et al., 2021; TAYLOR, 2019; VAN LAAR et al., 2017; MATTURRO et al., 2019; GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
Criticality and reflection	(VALERO et al., 2020)
Reflective thinking	(CARROLL et al., 2007)
8. Analytical skills (43%)	
Nomenclature	References
Analytical skills and problem-solving	(SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; AHMED et al., 2012)
Problem analysis	(HAZZAN, 2021; STRAY et al., 2021; SEDELMAIER and LANDES, 2014)
Analytical skills	(VALERO et al., 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019)
Logical thinking	(SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018)
9. Problem-solving (43%)	
Nomenclature	References
Problem-solving	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; VAN LAAR et al., 2017; CARTER, 2011)
Conflict management	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; TAYLOR, 2019; GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
Solve complex problems	(VALERO et al., 2020)
Problem-solving and conflict management	(MATTURRO et al., 2019)
10. Professionalism (39%)	
Nomenclature	References
Professionalism	(CARTER, 2011)
Civic and public engagement	(BYRNE et al., 2020)
Negotiation	(MATTURRO et al., 2019)

Professionalism and work ethic	(TAYLOR, 2019)
Business meetings	(SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018)
Business creation	(FREITAS et al., 2018)
Personal and social responsibility	(VAN LAAR et al., 2017)
To act entrepreneurially	(CUKIERMAN and PALMIERI, 2014)
Enterprise	(CARROLL et al., 2007)
11. Flexibility (39%)	
Nomenclature	References
Flexibility	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; VALERO et al., 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019)
Openness to changes	(HAZZAN, 2021)
Adaptability	(STRAY et al., 2021; CARROLL et al., 2007)
Flexibility and adaptability	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021)
Openness to changes and adaptability	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020)
Change Management	(MATTURRO et al., 2019)
12. Autonomy (35%)	
Nomenclature	References
Autonomy	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; CARROLL et al., 2007)
Independence	(HAZZAN, 2021; KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020)
Self-management	(TAYLOR, 2019)
13. Multidisciplinary thinking (30%)	
Nomenclature	References
Multidisciplinary thinking	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; TAYLOR, 2019; CARTER, 2011)
Cultural adaptability	(BYRNE et al., 2020)
Diverse knowledge and cultural	(VALERO et al., 2020)
Search and classification of information from different sources	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
14. Interpersonal (30%)	
Nomenclature	References
Interpersonal	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; AHMED et al., 2012; CARROLL et al., 2007)
Social	(VALERO et al., 2020)
15. Ethics (26%)	
Nomenclature	References
Ethics	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; VALERO et al., 2020; SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018; MATTURRO et al., 2019; CUKIERMAN and PALMIERI, 2014)
16. Motivation (22%)	
Nomenclature	References
Motivation	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013; CARTER, 2011)
17. Customer orientation (22%)	
Nomenclature	References

Customer orientation	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
Client management and client expectations	(GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
18. Results orientation (22%)	
Nomenclature	References
Results Orientation	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
Evaluation/communication of results	(GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
19. Commitment (17%)	
Nomenclature	References
Commitment	(MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
Responsibility	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020)
20. Initiative (17%)	
Nomenclature	References
Initiative	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021; MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
21. Decision-making (17%)	
Nomenclature	References
Decision-making	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; MATTURRO et al., 2019; VAN LAAR et al., 2017; GONZÁLEZ-MORALES et al., 2011)
22. Methodical (13%)	
Nomenclature	References
Methodical	(MATTURRO et al., 2019; MATTURRO et al., 2015; MATTURRO, 2013)
23. Personal (13%)	
Nomenclature	References
Personal	(SEDELMAIER and LANDES, 2014)
Personal skills	(GAROUSI et al., 2019)
Emotional intelligence	(TAYLOR, 2019)
24. Attention (9%)	
Nomenclature	References
Attention to details	(STRAY et al., 2021; KONINGS and LEGG, 2020)
25. Work under pressure (9%)	
Nomenclature	References
Work under pressure	(KHAKUREL and PORRAS, 2020)
Dealing with challenges	(ZHENG et al., 2015)
26. Persistence (9%)	
Nomenclature	References
Persistence	(HAZZAN, 2021)
Ability to work with constraints	(GROENEVELD et al., 2021)
27. Listening (9%)	
Nomenclature	References
Listening	(MATTURRO et al., 2019)
Good listener	(CAEIRO-RODRÍGUEZ et al., 2021)
28. Technical literacy (9%)	
Nomenclature	References

Information technology and communication literacy	(VAN LAAR et al., 2017)
Research skills and science communication	(FREITAS et al., 2018)
29. Environmental awareness (9%)	
Nomenclature	References
Environmental awareness	(KONINGS and LEGG, 2020; VALERO et al., 2020)
30. Debating (4%)	
Nomenclature	References
Debating	(SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018)
31. Feedback (4%)	
Nomenclature	References
Feedback	(SCHIPPER and VAN DER STAPPEN, 2018)
32. Stress management (4%)	
Nomenclature	References
Stress management	(MATTURRO et al., 2019)
33. Metacognition (4%)	
Nomenclature	References
Metacognition	(VAN LAAR et al., 2017)